

Gastronomic tourist experience through the colour of food

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Goal and objectives of the dissertation

Goal

This PhD thesis is presented as a collection of research papers. The articles are published, and/or presented, in a variety of journals and conferences of different, but overlapping, fields of inquiry, such as food science and gastronomy, tourism, uncertainty management, systems and technology. This thesis is a step toward the possible convergence of tourism, sensory science, engineering, and psychology representing various fields to collaborate on the research of behaviour.

Objectives

1. To evaluate how food colour influences the gastronomic tourism experience for visitors from a pre-travel standpoint.
2. To evaluate how the cues of a food item on social media influence tourists' decision-making.

Finally, according to the results, the problem of promoting gastronomic tourism is discussed. The importance of both the culinary image and the image of the destination is explored.

Methodology

The thesis utilizes multiple methods (e.g., correlational, experimental) and gastronomic contexts (e.g., beer, speciality dishes, such as Spinach with pees, Paella). Furthermore, these contributions are achieved by means of experimental and correlational studies, as well as by utilizing algorithms that allow him to track specific relationships between colours and variables of interest.

Results

The results contribute to our understanding of how food colour, in addition to other variables, can influence the expectations and behaviour of consumers (and in some cases potential tourists). Furthermore, the work maps the semantic, hedonic, and sensory space of some representative colours. The results show that when the food is unfamiliar, colour is an important factor in influencing food emotions and perhaps consumption decisions (Casales-Garcia, et al. 2023a). For example, if the food is dark green, potential tourists unfamiliar with the food may experience a feeling of disgust. Moreover, not only the colour of the food is a factor, but also the shape of the containers that contain it as an extrinsic element can influence the taste (sweet, sour, etc.), for example on beer (Casales-Garcia et al., 2023b).

Theoretical conclusions

People's perceptions and cultural backgrounds determine how much food they eat and what they choose to consume, which in turn affects how they ultimately decide which restaurant or culinary destination to make a trip to. The contribution of this study is to show how perceptions of food colour influence decisions about restaurants and travel destinations, either positively or negatively (Casales-Garcia, 2023).

Furthermore, the gastronomy aesthetics may become crucial when a consumer encounters fresh, unexplored gastronomy. The findings of this PhD thesis made it clear how important it is to keep researching colour-related moods, how they can impact and influence people's behaviour when selecting travel destinations, and which destination is more appealing when considering food colours in the regional cuisine (Casales-Garcia, 2023). Additionally, based on the results, we can observe how colour can influence the familiarity, beauty, and aesthetics of food since people can use colour to distinguish between familiar and unfamiliar foods and evaluate them based on established cultural norms (Casales-Garcia, et al., 2023).

Practical application of the dissertation

Currently, 496 million images may be found while searching for #food on Instagram. As a result, choosing the ideal image to promote a destination is more difficult. Furthermore, this task becomes more sophisticated if it is tailored to a particular consumer, considering factors like age, nationality, etc. Thus, this is a step toward giving marketing experts the tools they need to improve the way they advertise culinary goods and craft a compelling culinary image of a restaurant or travel destination. It is crucial to take colour and mood into account. Additionally, this study is a step toward the development of the destinations' culinary legacy, which can support the creation of an intriguing local character that appeals to both residents and visitors (Casales-Garcia, 2023).

Finally, we conclude that to effectively advertise and market destinations, destination marketers must understand gastronomic products, including local cuisine and food culture (Horng & Tsai, 2010; Okumus *et al.* 2007; Chang & Mak, 2018). Because of this, marketing experts should have access to tools that will enable them to effectively advertise dishes and craft an appealing culinary image for a restaurant or travel location. Further investigation on the impact of colour on travel decisions is our aim.

Content of the dissertation

Abstract of Chapter 1. Gastronomy and Gastronomic Tourism

The chapter reviews the importance of tourism as a sector for economic recovery post-Covid-19 is reviewed; It answers the question "What is gastronomy?" and highlights the emergence of gastronomic tourism followed by a summary of the history of gastronomy in civilisation.

Abstract of Chapter 2. Promoting the Gastronomy Image of a Destination

The chapter reviews the promoting of gastronomic tourism destinations through their gastronomic image and food-porn. To encourage people to visit a place, they have to believe that the only way to taste the original cuisine at the destination is by travelling there. Hence, marketers in gastronomic tourism must create the idea that tourists better taste the traditional dishes from a specific cuisine on the spot.

Abstract of Chapter 3. How Food Colour Affects Tourists' Behaviour

The chapter considers the close connection between colour and cuisine, food is without a doubt the first resource that people have sought. Food colour preference in humans is thought to have developed over a considerable amount of time during human evolution and is believed to be influenced by both genetically inherited features and experiential instruction.

Abstract of Chapter 4. Quality and Satisfaction on the Cruise Industry

The chapter reviews the customers' satisfaction on cruise ships regarding on-board services and facilities constitutes one of the most important aspects for cruise companies.

Abstract of Chapter 5. Assessing the Influence of Colour and Glass Type on Beer Expectations

The chapter examines the relationship between beer colour and glass type in the formation of beer expectancies. In line with earlier studies, we hypothesize that colour mitigates the effects of glass type on beer expectancies because it is a prominent characteristic in expectations for food and beverages. According to our findings, glass type affects every variable except intensity and willingness to pay (WT),

whereas colour affects the expectations based on sensory discrimination, hedonic evaluations, and willingness to pay (WTP) ratings (Casales-Garcia *et al.*, 2023b).

Abstract of Chapter 6. A Study On How Food Colour May Determine The Categorization Of A Dish: Predicting Meal Appeal From Colour Combinations

The chapter research analyses the significance of food colour in these kinds of preferences. In order to achieve this, an automatic algorithm is used to process a collection of dish photographs to assign an adjective that corresponds to the dish's classification and is related to the colour palettes in the image. The Kobayashi model of harmonic colour pairings serves as the foundation for the automatic labelling of adjectives that can be used to describe a dish. The study also establishes a rating model to estimate the degree to which a user would prefer the colour palettes generated, thereby verifying that the colour palettes computed for every image are harmonic (Casales-Garcia *et al.*, 2022b).

Abstract of Chapter 7. Extracting Feeling from Colour Food

The chapter presents the implementation of QCharm, a qualitative colour theory with cognitive inspiration that creates harmonic colour palettes using a qualitative colour description model. QCharm harmonious colour palettes can have cognitive keywords associated with a sentiment or lifestyle given to them using Kobayashi's colour space. After using QCharm on multiple food photos, a set of emotions is produced (Casales-Garcia, *et al.*, 2019a).

Abstract of Chapter 8. A Study On How Colour Food Influences Gastronomic Tourism In Spanish And Latino-American People

An exploratory study is provided on how the perception of food colour influences the mood of Spanish and Latino individuals. A survey is conducted that includes questions on the participant's feelings as well as pictures of dishes. The survey's results analysis validates that people's perceptions of food are influenced by colour. Therefore, selecting food colours that make people feel good can be useful in drawing foodies to a specific location (Casales-Garcia, *et al.* 2023a).

Abstract of Chapter 9. Analysing Food-Porn Images for Users' Engagement in the Food Business

The chapter presented is an analysis method for food-porn photos and comments from the cooking school Getcookingcanada's Instagram account. Our method counts the likes on each image, examines the comments on each publication, and processes the published photographs to extract colour parameters. All of them were combined into a dataset, and techniques were used to examine correlations between the data: regression analysis, ANOVA, and sentiment analysis of the dataset's comments were used to elucidate the relationship between the number of likes and the sentiment gleaned from the food photos (Casales-Garcia *et al.*, 2022a).

Abstract of Chapter 10. Analysis of the satisfaction of the clients of Tourist Cruises and proposals of Improvements

This chapter was carried out as part of an extensive search for surveys on the main services provided by a passenger. Through a descriptive analysis of the data collected, we have determined that the services of excursions and animation have received the lowest ratings. Improvements in these areas are necessary as they will be the ones that will boost cruise passengers' contentment (Casales-Garcia, *et al.*, 2019b).

Abstract of Chapter 11. Econometric Model of Cruise ship satisfaction

Cruise tourism continues to be an open issue for research because it is one of the tourist modalities with the highest potential for recovery after the epidemic. The methodology used to analyse the data was an

econometric model. The goal is to construct an economic model employing some of the most important variables for cruise passenger satisfaction to explain it (Casales-Garcia, et al., 2022c).

Abstract of Chapter 12. Employment Opportunities in the Andalusian Cruise Tourism Industry. Post-Covid19 and Andalusian Potential Challenges

The cruise industry offers a wide range of career opportunities, although the industry lacks specialized and technical training. This chapter has investigated these opportunities. Consequently, the job prospects for Andalusian professionals in the naval sector industry can be effectively and practically specified with the implementation of an appropriate strategy. These professionals must also overcome the challenges that arise in the wake of COVID-19 (Casales-Garcia et al., 2021).

Abstract of Chapter 13. Conclusions and future work

This section is divided into Conclusions and Future Work regarding the topic of Food Colour and Conclusion regarding the topic of Quality and Satisfaction.

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